

K/ha, and 18 kg S/ha.

Urea to 100 kg N/ha was added with the 17:17:17 mixture and with DAP. Muriate of potash at 42 kg K/ha was applied for all treatments. Gypsum,

elemental S, and calcium oxide were applied basally.

Urea at 100 kg N/ha plus gypsum at 1/2 t/ha overwhelmingly increased yield (see table). Gypsum at 1/2 t/ha with

17:17:17 mixture and DAP equaled urea at 100 kg N/ha plus gypsum at 1/4 t/ha. S enhanced yield more than Ca. Gypsum is an easily available and cheaper source of S than elemental S. □

Efficiency of phosphorus form combined with organic manure in rice - rice cropping

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We compared direct and residual effects of phosphate rock and superphosphate on IR20 in 1982-83 kharif (wet season) and rabi (dry season). Treatments were imposed on the kharif crop, residual effects were studied on the rabi crop in a randomized block design replicated three times.

Both crops received 100 kg N and 42 kg K/ha. Soil was clay loam, with 220 kg available N/ha, 4.3 kg P/ha, 271 kg available K/ha, and pH 8.0. Organic manures were farmyard manure

Grain yield and return of phosphate and organic manure combinations. Coimbatore, India, 1982-83.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Return ^a / \$ invested
	Kharif	Rabi	
Farmyard manure alone	4.7	4.7	1.87
Farmyard manure + superphosphate	5.4	5.0	2.06
Farmyard manure + rock phosphate	4.9	5.4	2.10
Compost alone	4.7	4.8	1.98
Compost + superphosphate	5.6	4.6	2.03
Compost + rock phosphate	5.2	5.0	2.12
Greenleaf manure alone	5.9	4.8	1.93
Green leaf + superphosphate	5.9	4.9	2.09
Green leaf + rock phosphate	5.0	5.3	2.03
Superphosphate alone	5.4	4.9	2.10
Rock phosphate alone	4.4	4.9	1.90
Control (no Organic manure)	4.0	4.0	1.54
CD (0.05)	0.1	0.5	

^a Av of 2 seasons.

(FYM) — 0.05% N, 0.11% P, 0.42% K; composted water hyacinth — 1.5% N, 0.34% P, 1.25% K; and leucaena green leaf manure — 3.0% N, 1.7% P, 2.08% K.

The efficiency of superphosphate and rock phosphate improved when they were combined with organic manures (see table). Superphosphate applied with organic manure had highest direct effect. Superphosphate with leucaena green leaf

manure was best. Rock phosphate efficiency improved with composted water hyacinth.

Residual effects of all organic manures and P were equal. Rock phosphate with organic manure was better in obtaining high grain yield. FYM was the best in improving rock phosphate efficiency. Composted water hyacinth with rock phosphate gave the highest net return. □

Effect of Azospirillum on ASD16 rice

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We evaluated the effect of *Azospirillum* on grain yield of ASD16 (110 d duration) Jun-Oct 1986. Five N levels (0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha) and 4

Azospirillum treatments (control, seed treatment, seedling dip, and field application) were examined in a split-plot design with 3 replications. Available NPK was 298-75-164 kg/ha.

Yield differences due to *Azospirillum* treatment as well as the interaction between *Azospirillum* and N levels were not significant. All four N treatments were significantly superior to the control. □

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Rice-based fish and vegetable cropping system in coastal saline soils

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In the coastal saline soils of the Sundarbans, rice is grown only during the monsoon season. No crop is grown during the winter and summer seasons because good quality irrigation water is lacking and soil salinity is high. Saline water is plentiful throughout the year.

Yield and income with different rice - fish - vegetable cropping systems in Barrackpore, India, 1982-85.

Cropping pattern	Yield (t/ha)	Gross return (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
Rice	3.4	398.00	150.00
Rice + freshwater fish	3.4	855.30	395.30
Rice - brackish water fish	0.5		
Rice - brackish water fish	3.4	1297.60	624.60
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	3.4	1754.90	869.90
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	3.4	2594.30	1294.30
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	0.5		
Rice + freshwater fish - brackish water fish	10.7		